

FEATURES OF THE PHYSICAL DEVELOPMENT OF CHILDREN IN THE ORGANIZATION OF THE PEDAGOGICAL PROCESS OF PRESCHOOL EDUCATION

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Abstract: This article talks about the originality of the physical development of children in the organization of the pedagogical process of preschool education. The physical education of preschool children occupies a special place in the general system of education and upbringing.

Keywords: Physical education, physical fitness, physical maturity, physical activity, educator, child, health, fitness, endurance, maturity.

Аннотация: В данной статье говорится об своеобразии физического развития детей в организации педагогического процесса дошкольного образования. Физическое воспитание дошкольников занимает особое место в общей системе обучения и воспитания.

Ключевые слова: Физическое воспитание, физическая подготовленность, физическая зрелость, двигательная активность, воспитатель, ребенок, здоровье, подготовленность, выносливость, зрелость.

In order to further develop science in our country, to educate our youth as possessors of deep knowledge, high spirituality and culture, to rapidly continue the work we have started on the formation of a competitive economy and to raise it to a new, modern level, our honorable president Sh. Mirziyoyev announced the year 2020 in our country. It was announced as "the year of development of science, enlightenment and digital economy". In addition, in his speech, our president said: "We should carry out large-scale work on the development and reform of the specified areas as a priority during 2020. we need to reach 60% per year..." and gave

several tasks and suggestions to further increase the responsibility of personnel working in the field of preschool education.

Physical education of preschool children has a special place in the general system of education and upbringing. An important task that determines the importance of physical education as the basis of all-round development is a child who knows his movements well, who likes physical exercises, who is independently oriented to his environment, who has the ability to learn at school and later has an active creative ability. is to form a healthy child.

The priority of working with preschool children should be physical education of preschool children, which is aimed at increasing the resistance of the child's body to the negative factors of the external and internal environment, mastering theoretical knowledge in the field of physical culture, and forming physical culture. development of movement abilities, physical and mental qualities and abilities, interest and need for physical improvement, comprehensive formation of the child's personality.

The whole set of physical education tools, including the implementation of daily routines, health and fitness activities, provision of necessary physical loads, rational nutrition should be aimed at the main task - raising a healthy child. Only by implementing a comprehensive approach, it is possible to achieve the main tasks of education and recreation: to strengthen the physical and mental health of children, to increase their optimal physical development and mobility.

The basis of the child's physical health should be considered the level of development and characteristics of his organs and systems. The level of development is determined by a program that is specific to the nature of each child and is related to his basic needs. This is the satisfaction of basic basic needs, which is a condition for the child's individual development. A prerequisite for the complete mental health of children is a state of mental comfort and psychological well-being that ensures adequate regulation of their behavior in the course of various activities. The spiritual component of human health is characterized by their attitude to the

educational process, as well as their compliance with generally accepted norms of behavior, which are directly related to the development of motivational and semantic areas of a preschool child.

Theory and technology of children's physical education as an integrated science involves a wide range of issues, the study of which is interdependent

related to the achievement of subjects. Research on the theory and technology of children's physical education special sciences and methods - sociology, psychology, neuropsychology, physiology, sports methodology, medical control, etc. are used.

The relevance of the research problem, the purpose of the research, scientific innovation and practical importance, its subject and object, hypothesis and experimental begins with a short introduction that reveals its purpose.

The method of studying and summarizing advanced pedagogical experience is based on the study and understanding of theoretical and practical literature. Literary sources generalization and analysis to a deeper understanding of the problem of physical education allows. Most of the pedagogical studies we will consider in more detail applied methods.

Monitoring can be direct, mediated, open, hidden. He is an educator and develop a fact-finding system that includes monitoring the child's activities specially organized with exit. Pedagogical observation is convenient for you, in a natural environment allows you to study the questions you are interested in. What was observed in the process of observation It is recommended to use different methods for registration: video, audio recording, photography and filming, etc. Parameters of movement, organism functional status, time of certain types of activity are taken into account. For example: psychophysical qualities, indicators of physical fitness are measured; measure carried out: the vital capacity of the lungs using spirometry; hand muscle strength - using a hand dynamometer; organization of movement time indicators for individual parts of the body when performing various forms - stopwatch, etc. Thus, the theory of physical education is different instrumental and

instrumental for measuring physiological and psychophysiological states non-existent means are used.

The results of observation are recorded in a diary, protocol, matrix record or journal will be done. Tracking data record time, location, number of participants, and tracking quality notes. Interview as a research method to study the personality of children and educators is used. The purpose of the research should be determined based on the interview, for this it is important to think about the questions in the interview and put them correctly. For example, if the teacher asks the child how the children spread around the hall, he answers gives: "Good, even, right", i.e. emphasizes the quality parameters of the movement.

If you ask a child where the children run from the hall, he replies, "There's no one around to avoid bumping into another kid." After recording the results of the interview, analyze the recordings you better do it. Assistant (educator or preschool educational institution a possible transcript of the interview by one of the employees). Conversation results can be shown in tables. His results are re-mathematical can work.

Questionnaire as a research method. Questionnaires in the physical education of children widely used. The survey has specially selected questions and possible consisting of standard answers.

The principles of physical education make a person a perfect person in every way to develop children's physical abilities, movement skills and abilities which helps to develop, educate the child's personality together and individually It is intended to approach the implementation of comprehensive education holds This approach to the system of physical education is unique to children characteristics, characteristics of young developmental stages, this or that of life types of physical education activities chosen as the main activity during the period also depends on the characteristics.

The principles of physical education, in accordance with it, in relation to the educator laws, regulations and requirements are formed, revealing its vital forces,

harmonious development, comprehensive physical preparation of the child for the future life its activity is determined. General pedagogical didactic in physical education same as principles (consciousness and activity, visibility, presence, etc.). as well as the special ones that represent the unique laws of physical education there is. Let's list the main part of these principles: - comprehensive and harmonious development of the individual;

- connection between physical culture and life;
- the direction of improving the health of physical education;
- continuity and regular exchange of load and rest;
- gradual increase of developing, educational effects;
- cyclic structure of classes;
- age dependence of physical education directions.

General pedagogical principles

The principle of awareness and activity is meaningful for physical exercise and movement in children aimed at training the relationship. It was developed by P.F. Lesgaft, who compared consciousness with mechanical memorization of actions. Movement technique, sequence of its execution, muscles strengthening and awareness of one's own body is reflected in the child's body helps to form. Physical exercises to the body Realizing the healing effect, the child solves movement problems independently and creatively learns to solve. He learns spatial terminology, consciously chooses a reasonable method of movement; It is a combination of actions, comes up with their options, organizes familiar games and to themselves will be relevant.

P.F. Lesgaft teaching a child to do various things with words, actions and wrote that it is necessary to teach to be more independent in voluntary manifestations. The principle of activity is high independence, initiative and creativity in the child implies.

The principle of regularity and consistency is for all types of physical education mandatory: formation of movement skills, consolidation, regime. Systematic

knowledge, It is manifested in the interdependence of skills and qualifications. Preparation and a leading exercise system based on transitioning and mastering a new movement allows you to start learning the next, more complex material. Regularity, regularity, continuity of preschool physical education provides the principle of regularity. Physical education in all age groups a clear sequence of exercises, loads and rest is mandatory exchange, as well as consistency, continuity, reciprocity in the composition of the classes themselves should be monitored accordingly. Organize movement together with strengthening exercises daily, regular forms of child health and upbringing teaches to constantly monitor the regime, at the same time systematic finishing the training, the functional capabilities of his body and physical reduces readiness.

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